

WE OFFER UP TO
100,000€
EQUITY-FREE
FUNDING TO
OVER
90 PROJECTS!

OUR MISSION

We aim to empower a diverse community of multidisciplinary Universities & Research centers, SMEs & Startups and NGOs & foundations in the development of Next Generation Internet technologies and services, fostering transatlantic collaboration between the EU, USA and Canada.

ELIGIBLE KNOWLEDGE AREAS

HOW TO APPLY?

STEP 1

Find your EU or Canada partner through our BROKERAGE service.

STEP 2

Write your joint proposal

STEP 3

Submit your application before
18 DECEMBER 2023 17:00 CET / 10:00 CDT

DO YOU HAVE MORE QUESTIONS?

JOIN US FOR OUR WEBINAR

WWW.NGISARGASSO.EU

HELPDESK@NGISARGASSO.EU

DISCOVER OUR
TRAILBLAZING INNOVATORS!

Be part of a community
where limits are just a
concept.

APPLY NOW!

